

ANTIBIOTIC PROPHYLAXIS IN SURGICAL SITE INFECTION PREVENTION: A PROSPECTIVE OBSERVATIONAL STUDY OF CLEAN AND CLEAN-CONTAMINATED CASES**Bhanavath Abhilash*¹, Manda Abhishek¹, Thota Lakshmi¹, Asfiya Saba¹, Dr. R. L. Manisha²**¹Malla Reddy College of Pharmacy, Maisammaguda, Hyderabad-500100, Telangana, India.²Associate Professor, Department of Pharmacy Practice, Malla Reddy College of Pharmacy, Maisammaguda, Secunderabad-500100, Telangana, India.***Corresponding Author: Bhanavath Abhilash**

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ABSTRACT

Background: Surgical Site Infections (SSIs) remain a major cause of postoperative morbidity, especially in clean and clean-contaminated surgeries. Optimal antibiotic prophylaxis is essential to prevent SSIs and reduce hospital burden. **Objective:** To compare the effectiveness of preoperative prophylactic antibiotics versus postoperative therapeutic antibiotics in preventing SSIs and to evaluate the influence of risk factors, timing, and antibiotic choice. **Methods:** A prospective observational study was conducted for six months in the Department of General Surgery, Malla Reddy Hospital. A total of 250 patients were allocated into two equal groups based on antibiotic strategy.

- Group A: Received a single dose of IV pre-operative Antibiotic (ceftriaxone) 30–60 minutes before surgical incision.
- Group B: Received only postoperative antibiotic therapy (cefotaxime/ceftriaxone/ fluroquinolones) for 2–3 days without pre-operative prophylaxis.

Demographics, comorbidities, surgery type, antibiotic timing, and SSI occurrence were assessed. Statistical tests included Chi-square, ANOVA, and logistic regression. **Results:** Group A demonstrated a significantly lower SSI rate (23.2%) compared to Group B (48.8%) ($p < 0.05$). Clean-contaminated surgeries and comorbidities (DM, HTN) were associated with higher SSI risk. Optimal timing (≤ 30 min) and IV route were strongly protective.

Conclusion: Preoperative IV ceftriaxone given within 30 - 60 minutes before surgical incision is markedly more effective than postoperative therapeutic antibiotics in preventing SSIs. Adherence to prophylaxis timing and antibiotic stewardship is essential to improve surgical outcomes.

KEYWORDS: SSI, prophylaxis, ceftriaxone, clean surgeries, and antibiotic timing.**INTRODUCTION**

Surgical Site Infections (SSIs) are among the most frequent postoperative complications and contribute significantly to global morbidity and healthcare burden.^[1] SSIs occur within 30 days of surgery, or within one year when implants are involved, and are classified by the CDC as superficial incisional, deep incisional, or organ/space infections.^[2] These infections arise from endogenous patient flora or exogenous sources such as contaminated instruments or breaks in aseptic technique.^[3]

SSIs account for approximately 20% of hospital-acquired infections worldwide, with reported incidence rates of 2–5% in developed nations and up to 10–15% in developing countries, including India.^[4–6] They prolong hospitalization, delay recovery, increase costs, and may lead to severe complications such as sepsis. SSI risk is influenced by multiple factors, including age, diabetes, obesity, malnutrition, immunosuppression, prolonged operative duration, emergency procedures, and bacterial virulence.^[8–11]

Wound classification strongly predicts SSI risk. Clean surgeries have low infection rates, whereas clean-contaminated surgeries—where controlled entry into respiratory, gastrointestinal, or genitourinary tracts occurs—have significantly higher risk due to exposure to endogenous flora.^[12]

Surgical Antibiotic Prophylaxis (SAP) is a proven preventive strategy aimed at achieving bactericidal drug concentrations at the time of incision. International guidelines from WHO, CDC, NICE, and ASHP recommend administering prophylactic antibiotics within 30–60 minutes before incision, with a single preoperative dose being adequate for most surgeries.^[13–17] Cephalosporins such as cefazolin and ceftriaxone are widely preferred due to their broad coverage and favourable pharmacokinetics.^[18]

Despite strong evidence, inappropriate antibiotic use remains common, including incorrect timing, unnecessary postoperative continuation, and the use of broad-spectrum agents, contributing to antimicrobial resistance (AMR).^[19,20] Variation in prophylactic practices across hospitals highlights the need for real-world evaluation of antibiotic strategies, particularly in clean and clean-contaminated surgeries, which make up a large portion of surgical procedures.^[21]

Given these concerns, the present study aims to assess SSI incidence in clean and clean-contaminated surgeries and compare outcomes between preoperative prophylactic antibiotic administration and postoperative therapeutic antibiotic therapy. The study also evaluates patient risk factors, antibiotic timing, route of administration, and surgical characteristics to support rational antibiotic use and improve infection control practices. Surgical Site Infections (SSIs) continue to be a major concern in perioperative care and remain one of the most common complications following surgical procedures.^[1] These infections may arise from the patient's endogenous flora or from exogenous sources such as contaminated operating room equipment, surgical instruments, or inadequate aseptic practices.^[3]

METHODS AND MATERIALS

Study Design and Setting

A prospective observational study was conducted over six months in the Department of General Surgery, Malla Reddy Hospital, Hyderabad, after approval from the Institutional Ethics Committee.

Sample and Group Allocation

A total of 250 patients undergoing clean or clean-contaminated surgeries were enrolled by convenience sampling and divided into two equal groups.

Group A: (Prophylaxis): Received preoperative antibiotics only.

Group B: (Therapeutic): Received postoperative antibiotic therapy only.

The Antibiotics administered during the study included (Trade Names & Manufacturers)

CEFTRIAZONE – MONOCEF (Aristo Pharma Ltd., India)

CEFOTAXIME – TAXIM (Alkem Laboratories Ltd., India)

CIPROFLOXACIN – CIPROFLOX (Bayer Pharmaceuticals, Germany)

OFLOXACIN – OFLOX (Cipla Ltd., India)

CLINDAMYCIN – DALACIN-C (Pfizer Healthcare India)

VANCOMYCIN – VANLID (Cipla Ltd., India)

Antibiotics were administered as per hospital availability and standard clinical practice.

Conflict of Interest.

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest. The mention of trade names and manufacturers is solely for identification purposes and does not imply any endorsement. The study was conducted independently, and no financial or material support was received from any pharmaceutical company.

Intervention

Group A received a single IV dose of CEFTRIAZONE (MONOCEF) 30–60 min before incision with no postoperative antibiotics.

Group B received postoperative antibiotics (MONOCEF / TAXIM / CIPROFLOX / OFLOX) for 2–3 days; VANLID or DALACIN-C was used in cephalosporin-resistant cases.

Data Collection

Data included demographics, comorbidities, surgical category, antibiotic regimen, timing of administration, and postoperative outcomes.

Outcome Measures

Primary: Surgical site infection within 30 days.

Secondary: Influence of timing, comorbidities, and postoperative hospital stay.

Statistical Analysis

Analysis was performed using Chi-square, ANOVA, logistic regression, and Mann-Whitney U test; significance set at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

➤ The total number of patients included in this study were (n=250).

Fig-1: Distribution of patients with infection rate according to age group.

INFERENCE

The age-wise distribution of the study participants indicates that the majority of patients (50.0%) fall within

the age range of 36-60 years. Patients aged up to 35 years account for 28.4% of the total, while those above 60 years comprise 21.6% of the population.

Comparison Between Gender (N=250)

Fig-2: Distribution of patients with infection rate according to gender.

INFERENCE: Gender distribution among the study population reveals a higher representation of female

patients, constituting 65.2% of the total. Male patients account for 34.8% of the population.

Fig-3: Distribution patients with infection rate according to co-morbidities.

INFERENCE: The majority of patients (12.8%) have hypertension (HTN) is the most common conditions of the patients, respectively. Diabetes mellitus (DM) affects 9.2% of the patients, while thyroid conditions and

asthma are less prevalent, affecting 6.4% and 0.8% of the patients, respectively. The presence of multiple co-morbidities, such as HTN+DM, is relatively rare, occurring in only 1.2% of the patients.

OBJECTIVE-1.

Fig-4: Compare the infection rate between clean and clean contaminated surgeries.

✓ The graph illustrates the infection rates in Group A based on the type of surgery. It shows that patients who underwent clean contaminated surgeries experienced a significantly higher infection rate (26.32%) compared to those who underwent clean surgeries (18.37%).

✓ The graph illustrates the infection rates in Group B based on the type of surgery. It shows that patients who underwent clean contaminated surgeries experienced a higher infection rate (42.35%) compared to those who underwent clean surgeries (37.50%).

Fig-5: Distribution Based on the infection rate between Group A and Group B.

INFERENCE: The SSI infection distribution between the two groups indicates that the majority of infections occurred in Group B, accounting for 63.8% of the cases (51 cases). In contrast, Group A reported 36.2% of the cases (29 cases). This suggests that Group B had a higher incidence of SSI infections compared to Group A.

OBJECTIVE-2

Fig-6: Distribution of patients based on class of antibiotics.

INFERENCE: The distribution of patients by antibiotic class reveals that the majority were prescribed Cephalosporins, accounting for 233 patients, which represents a dominant portion of the prescriptions. This is followed by Penicillins with 13 patients. Other classes

such as Tetracycline, Fluoroquinolone, and Nitroimidazole were prescribed to only a minimal number of patients (1–2 cases each), indicating that Cephalosporins were overwhelmingly the most commonly used antibiotic class in this study.

Antibiotics Prescription Distribution (Total Patients: 250)

Fig 7: Distribution of patients based on antibiotics.

INFERENCE: The antibiotics prescription distribution among the 250 patients shows that the majority were prescribed Ceftriaxone (Monocef), accounting for 68.0% of cases (170 patients). Cefotaxime was the second most prescribed antibiotic with 22.8% (57 patients). Other antibiotics such as Augmentin (5.4%), Magnet forte (1.2%), Metrogyl, and Cifran (each 0.8%) were prescribed less frequently, while Cefoperazone+sulbactum and Doxycycline were the least prescribed, each at 0.4%. This indicates a strong preference for Ceftriaxone (Monocef) as the primary antibiotic in the treatment regimen.

OBJECTIVE-3.

Fig-8: Distribution of patients based on route of Administration of antibiotic.

INFERENCE: The route of antibiotic administration among the study participants indicates that the majority of patients (86.4%) received antibiotics through the intravenous (IV) route. In contrast, only 13.6% of the

patients were administered antibiotics via the oral route. This suggests a strong preference for IV administration, likely reflecting the clinical need for rapid or more effective delivery of antibiotics in the majority of cases.

OBJECTIVE-4

Fig-9: Distribution of patients based on timing of administration of preoperative antibiotics.

INFERENCE: The timing of antibiotic administration before surgical incision indicates that a majority of patients (81.6%) received antibiotics 30 minutes before

incision, while a smaller proportion (18.4%) received them 1 hour before incision.

Fig-10: Distribution of patients based on duration of hospital stay after postoperative antibiotics.

Figure 4.1.36: Distribution based on duration of hospital stay after postoperative antibiotics

INFERENCE: The post-operative duration of hospitalisation indicates that the majority of patients were discharged within 4 to 5 days, with 27.2% hospitalized for 5 days and 26.0% for 4 days. A smaller

proportion remained for 3 days (15.2%) and 6 days (10.8%), while 18.8% required more than 6 days. Only 2.0% of patients were discharged as early as 2 days post-operation.

Overall outcomes of infection rate with its P-value and significance.

S.No	Outcomes	Test Performed	P-Value	Significance
1	Distribution Based On Age	Anova Test	0.00000496	Significant
2	Distribution Based On Gender	Chi-Square Test	0.00000153	Significant
3	Distribution Based On Co-Morbidities	Chi-Square Test	0.05	Significant
4	Compare The Infection Rate Between Clean And Clean Contaminated Surgeries	Chi-Square Test	0.00257	Significant
5	Infection Distribution Between Group A And Group B	Chi-Square Test	0.0044	Significant
6	Distribution Based On Systems	Chi-Square Test	0.0006	Significant
7	Distribution Based On Antibiotics	Chi-Square Test	0.0023	Significant
8	Distribution Based On Class Of Antibiotics	Chi-Square Test	0.000028	Significant
9	Distribution Based On Route Of Administration Of Antibiotic	Chi-Square Test	0.001	Significant
10	Distribution Based On Timing Of Administration Of Preoperative Antibiotics	Logistic Regression	0.015	Significant
11	Distribution Based On Duration Of Hospital Stay After Postoperative Antibiotics	Mann-Whitney U Test	0.000024	Significant

DISCUSSION

The present study provides important insights into the effectiveness of preoperative antibiotic prophylaxis in preventing Surgical Site Infections (SSIs) in clean and clean-contaminated surgeries. The findings clearly demonstrate that administering a single dose of intravenous ceftriaxone within 30–60 minutes before surgical incision significantly reduces SSI incidence compared with postoperative therapeutic antibiotic administration alone. This aligns with established recommendations from WHO, CDC, and ASHP, which emphasize correct timing as the most critical determinant of prophylactic success. The physiologic basis for this is well-recognized: antimicrobial concentrations must reach bactericidal levels in the tissues at the precise moment of incision to counter endogenous flora exposure.

The markedly higher SSI incidence observed in Group B supports the evidence that postoperative antibiotics cannot compensate for missed prophylaxis. Therapeutic antibiotics administered after contamination has occurred are less effective because bacterial colonization and early tissue adherence begin within minutes after incision. This highlights the fundamental difference between prophylaxis (prevention) and therapy (treatment) and underscores the need for strict perioperative timing protocols.

Clean-contaminated surgeries exhibited higher SSI rates than clean surgeries, which is consistent with global epidemiological patterns. Controlled entry into the gastrointestinal, respiratory, or genitourinary tracts increases exposure to polymicrobial flora, explaining the elevated risk. The identification of diabetes mellitus and hypertension as prominent comorbid risk factors further reinforces existing evidence that impaired microvascular circulation and reduced immune responsiveness delay healing and predispose to infection.

The predominance of ceftriaxone as the prophylactic agent reflects local clinical practice, and its effectiveness can be attributed to favourable pharmacokinetics, broad-spectrum activity, and excellent tissue penetration. However, practices such as prolonged postoperative use in some patients underscore ongoing challenges in antimicrobial stewardship. Excessive or inappropriate use of broad-spectrum agents contributes to antimicrobial resistance, a major public health threat. Overall, this study highlights the practical benefits of adhering to standardized SAP protocols and demonstrates that effective prophylaxis requires not only appropriate antibiotic selection but also precise timing, adequate dosing, and avoidance of unnecessary postoperative continuation. The results emphasize the importance of strengthening institutional guidelines and promoting continuous training for surgical teams to ensure consistent, evidence-based practice.

CONCLUSION

This study confirms that preoperative antibiotic prophylaxis is significantly more effective than postoperative therapeutic antibiotic administration in preventing SSIs in clean and clean-contaminated surgeries. A single dose of intravenous ceftriaxone administered within 30 minutes prior to incision provided optimal protection by achieving adequate bactericidal concentrations at the critical point of tissue exposure. Higher SSI rates in clean-contaminated procedures and among patients with comorbidities such as diabetes and hypertension highlight the need for individualized perioperative infection-prevention strategies.

The findings support global guidelines advocating timely prophylactic administration and discourage unnecessary postoperative antibiotic use, which offers no additional benefit and contributes to antimicrobial resistance. Implementing and reinforcing standardized antibiotic prophylaxis protocols can substantially reduce infection rates, shorten hospitalization, and enhance overall surgical outcomes. Strengthening antimicrobial stewardship programs and ensuring adherence among surgical teams are essential steps toward optimizing patient safety and improving the quality of surgical care.

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